

CASE STUDY

FACTORS AFFECTING EGGS HATCHABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) has been widely distributed in various parts of the world. Japanese quail has been used as a good source for egg and meat; it has been also used in many areas of biological research. It grows rapidly to maturity, the coturnix quail matures sexually of six weeks after hatching, its mating activity was at its maximum between 70 and 210 days of age. It has short incubation period and high rate of lay, the quail may lay more than 300 eggs in their first year of production. Its small size (150g at maturity) permits the storage of large numbers of birds in a relatively small space, consumes less feed in the adult stages which is much less than that of the chicken. Shortly, it is very economical bird as an experimental. Bird or as commercial producing bird. Obtaining a high production and reproduction performance in Japanese quail requires some collective factors work at its best. Behavioral factors are the most factors control bird to life and its welfare. Stocking density (space allowed for bird to live) even in cages or floor pens, mating ratio (male to female ratio) in the flock and type of housing are some of the most important elements of the managerial factor that control the production and reproduction performance of quail breeding flock. The former managerial factors are important to be consideration in Japanese quail to obtain body weight gain, high fertility, hatchability, egg production and better food utilization.

KEYWORDS: mortality, temperature, humidity, poor laying performance, short life span of chicks.

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INTRODUCTION

Long egg storage periods affect the pH of the albumen due to loss of carbon dioxide (Dawes, 1975), which is important in maintaining embryonic viability, and result in decreased hatchability (Heier & Jarp 2001). Eggs incubated on the day of lay produced heavier chicks than eggs stored for a number of days (Reis et al., 1997). Small eggs also produced smaller chickens with a lower performance than chickens hatched from larger eggs (Among et al., 1984, Farooq et al., 2001). Although numerous studies have shown that there is strong positive correlation between pre-incubation egg weight, length of storage periods, hatchlings weight and growth performance of different species of poultry (Farooq et al., 2001; Heier & Jarp, 2001), the effects of length of egg storage and hatching egg weight on the hatchability and subsequent growth performance of quail have not been fully investigated. Therefore, the objective of the present study was to examine the effect of egg weight and length of storage on hatchability and subsequent growth performance of quail (Table 1) and to determine the optimal pre-incubation egg storage period and optimal weight of eggs destined for hatching. Temperature is the most important factor affecting

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embryonic development, hatchability and post hatch performance. Optimum incubation temperature is normally defined as that required to achieve maximum hatchability.

Table1. Normal data on Japanese quail

Trait	Range
Body weight at one-day-old	6 ~ 8 g
Adult male	100 ~ 130 g
Adult female	120 ~ 160 g
Egg weight	9 ~ 10 g
Egg number/100 days	80 ~ 90
Age at sexual maturity	38 ~ 42 days of age
Life span	Max: 7 years in male
	Mean: 3 ~ 4 years

Table 2. Ingredient and chemical composition of the experimental diet

Ingredients	Dry matter %	Chemical composition	Dry matter mg/kg
Maize	54.88	Crude protein	220
Soya bean meal (48%)	24.00	Metabolisable energy (MJ/kg)	12.92
Full-fat soyabean	7.16	Crude fibre	28.4
Fish meal	6.00	Crude fat	89.0
Sunflower meal	0.50	Ash	41.4
Vegetable oil	4.86	Calcium	10.0
Dicalcium phosphate	1.30	Phosphorus	7.6
Sodium chloride	0.36	Lysine	11.4
Limestone, ground	0.55	Methionine	5.0
DL-methionine	0.17	Sodium	2.0
Oxiform Dry ¹			0.01
Vitamin and trace mineral premix ²			0.25
Coccidiostat ³			0.10

Hatching.

- Hatching refers to the production of baby chicks.
- Earlier days eggs were hatched by placing them under broody hens
- Only 10 to 12 eggs can be put under one hen
- This method of hatching is highly unsatisfactory for large scale production of baby chicks
- Incubators, which provide similar environment as that of broody hens, but more efficiency, are used at present for hatching eggs.

Incubators

- Incubators are the most important equipment in the hatching process.
- Incubator setting capacity ---- 14,000 to 100,000 eggs.
- During incubation, the hatching eggs are set vertically, with the large ends up and turned mechanically unit about three days prior to hatching (setting period).
- The eggs are then transferred to a hatcher (hatching period) in a horizontal position and not turned during the hatching process.
- Both setters and hatchers have forced-draft air circulation, automatic temperature, humidity and cooling controls.

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Temperatures

- The normal development of the embryo is dependent on the heat being held within a very narrow range in the incubator.
- 37. 2 to 37. 8 degree centigrade.
- Dry and wet bulb thermometers are used
- Low temperature ----- slows down the embryonic development.
- High temperature ----- hastens the embryonic development.

Humidity

- The amount of moisture in an incubator may be referred to as “relative humidity”.
- First 18 days ----- 60%
- Next 3 days ----- 70%
- In forced draft type incubators the temperature requirement decreases as the humidity increases.

Ventilation

- The free movement of oxygen, carbon dioxide and water vapor through the pores of the shell is important, since the developing embryo must be able to take in a constant supply of oxygen and release carbon dioxide and moisture.
- Oxygen content ----- 21%
- Carbon dioxide ----- 0.5%

Turning of eggs

- Fertile eggs are loaded with broad ends up.
- Modern incubators are provided with automatic turning of eggs at least 8 times a day.
- The egg trays turn through an angle of 90 degree.

Egg selection

- Poor quality hatching eggs do not hatch as well as eggs of good quality.
- The term “quality” refers to the condition outside the shell, the condition of the shell itself and that of the contents.
- Eggs with interior characteristics, as discussed in “selection and care of hatching eggs” should not be set.

Sanitation

- Eggs used for hatching should be clean and stored in clean containers in a sanitary egg holding room.
- Eggs contaminated with bacterial organisms usually do not hatch well and this poor quality is reflected in the chicks that do hatch.

Egg candling

- Candling chicken eggs on the 7th and 18th day of incubation, may be recommended for small poultry producers.
- Egg candling will detect infertile and early dead germs.
- Therefore, problems within the hatching flock can be identified without waiting until the incubation period is completed.

Fumigation

- Excessive and improper fumigation can result in high mortality in developing embryos.

1. Eggs are infertile.
2. Eggs are cracked and contents dried out.
3. Eggs are too old when set.
4. Eggs are held in extreme temperatures prior to incubation.

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5. Shells are contaminated.

Nutrition

Oluyemi and Roberts (1979) listed vitamins B2, B12 and D3 and minerals including calcium, magnesium and iron (Table 2) as being particularly important for good fertility and hatchability. Reduced feed supply however, leads to body weight loss and reduced libido in the male. Deficiencies of vitamins A and E adversely affect spermatogenesis and release of follicle stimulating hormone by the pituitary gland. Embryonic mortality at 26 days 14 and 15 of incubation was attributed to nutritional defects by Oluyemi and Roberts (1979). Reductions in fertility and hatchability and increased embryonic mortality were reported to be due to mineral imbalance, especially involving manganese (Offiong and Abed, 1980).

Storage period

Mc Donald and Arnot (1980) reported that length of pre-incubation storage has detrimental effect on hatchability of quail eggs in the sahel area and that quail eggs for incubation should not be stored at room temperature for more than 9 days, even in the coolest season.

Hatchability was generally good in eggs stored for 0 to 4 days, fair for those stored for 5 to 9 days, but dropped sharply after storage for 9 days. No egg hatched following preincubation storage of over 11 days. Petek *et al.* (2003) recommended that, storage period for quail eggs should not be more than 3 days. Hatchability of White Rock eggs was found to be significantly affected by storage period and incubation position but not by storage position. However, there was a tendency for eggs stored with the small-end-up to hatch better than those with small-end-horizontal. Maximum hatchability was obtained by combining a four day to six day storage period with the small-end-down incubation 27position. Oluyemi and George (1972) reported no significant interaction among storage period, storage position and incubation position.

Strain

Ayorinde and Okaeme (1984) reported marked variations in fertility, hatchability and embryonic mortality in local stocks of ash, black, pearl and white guinea fowl as well as among exotic (Golden Sovereign) varieties of guinea fowl. They observed that the pearl gave higher fertility and hatchability than the other varieties with a lower incidence of dead in shell. The effect of egg storage on fertility and hatchability is most severe in Coturnix quail than in Bobwhite quail (Reynnells *et al.*, 1977).

Incubation period for avian species

- Chicken ----- 21 days
- Japanese quail ----- 17 days
- Turkey ----- 28 days
- Guinea fowl ----- 26 days
- Goose ----- 28 to 32 days
- Duck ----- 28 days

REFERENCES

Among *et al.*, (1984). Effect of egg weight and pre-incubation storage period on fertility and hatchability of WLH eggs. *Ind. J. Poult. Sci.* 19, 108-111.

Ayorinde and Okaeme., (1984). The production potential of different varieties of the indigenous helmet guinea fowl (*N.m. galeata Pallas*) and the exotic Golden Sovereign (*N.m. meleagris*) in Nigeria. Proceedings 9th Annual Conference of the Nigerian Society for Animal Production, Nsukka, Nigeria, 65-72.

Farooq *et al.*, (2001). Egg and shell weight, hatching and production performance of Japanese broiler quail. *Sarhad J. Agric.* 17, 289-293.

Dawes, 1975, Dawes, C.M., (1975). Acid-base relationships within the avian egg. *Biology Rev.* 50, 351-376.

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Heier, B.T. & Jarp, J., (2001). An epidemiological study of the hatchability in broiler breeder flocks. *Poult. Sci.* 80, 1132-1138.

Mc Donald, E. & Arnot, E., (1980). Factors affecting the hatchability of eggs from broiler breeders. *Br. Poult. Sci.* 21, 37-53.

Narahari et al. (1988). Traits influencing performances of Japanese quail eggs. *British Poultry Science* 29:101-112.

Offiong and Abed, (1980). Fertility, hatchability and malformations in guinea fowl embryos as affected by dietary manganese. *Br Poult Sci.* 1980 Sep;21(5):371-5.

Oluyemi and Roberts., (1979). Poultry production in warm wet climate. Macmillan Publishers, Ltd., London, UK.

Oluyemi J. A. and George. O (1972). Some Factors Affecting Hatchability of Chicken Eggs. *Poult Sci* 1972 51:1762-1763; doi:10.3382/ps.0511762.

Reis et al., (1997). Effects of short storage conditions and broiler age on hatchability, hatching time and chick weight. *Poult. Sci.* 76, 1459-66.

Reynnells *et al.*, (1977). Effect of preincubation holding condition on hatchability of Bobwhite and coturnix quail eggs. *Poult. Sci.*, 56: 1750-1751.

Sefton A.E and Siegel., (1973). Mating behavior of Japanese quail. *Poult Sci.* 1973 May;52 (3):1001-7.

Petek *et al.* (2003). Effects of egg weight and length of storage on hatchability and subsequent growth performance of quail. *South Afr. J. Anim. Sci.*, 33: 242-247

Wilbor and Wilson., (1972). A Review of the Physiology of Coturnix (Japanese Quail). *World's Poultry Science Journal*, Volume 28, Issue 04, October 1972, pp 413-429.

Wilbor et al., (1961). Evaluation of Coturnix (Japanese quail) as pilot animal for poultry. *Poultry Science* 40:651-657.
